

Community Atlas of Commons

Chittorgarh

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An aerial photograph of a vast, flat landscape with a large, muddy-brown flooded area in the center. A concrete dam structure is visible on the left side of the flood, with a road leading to it. The surrounding land is covered in green vegetation and scattered trees. The sky is a pale, overcast blue.

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Chittorgarh

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Glossary

Community stewardship - Community stewardship is a concept where communities take the responsibility to form working relationships for inclusive and sustainable management of natural resources which lead to transformative change in regions and communities.

De facto use - a practice in use, regardless of its formal status

Ecosystem services - Positive benefits that humans receive from their natural environments, such as food, water, air purification and pollination.

Encroachment - An act of gradual or sudden intrusion on land or property by one who does not have material ownership or rights over it.

Formalisation of tenure - A process by which customary rights over resources are recognised within the formal institutional framework.

Landscape restoration - improving degraded lands at scale that restores and regenerates ecological health and enhances people's lives.

Livelihood resilience - The ability to adapt to and cope with shocks and disturbances in the environment.

Nomadic and semi-nomadic grazers - Livestock keepers or herders who move from place to place for livestock grazing on grasses and other vegetation.

Panchayat circle - The territorial area over which a Panchayat can exercise jurisdiction and control.

Participatory land management - A bottom-up method of governance of natural resources where local communities can effectively engage with and influence the decision-making processes.

Pastoral communities - Communities that herd domesticated livestock for livelihood.

Rainfed agriculture - Type of farming that relies exclusively or predominantly on rainfall as the source of irrigation.

Sustainable livelihoods - a livelihood can be called sustainable when it helps maintain or enhance one's capacities and assets. It also helps in recovering quickly from external shocks or stresses.

Traditional knowledge - The system of knowledge, skills, and practices of indigenous and local communities that have been passed down through generations.

Wasteland - Land deemed to be barren, unproductive or is uncultivated.

Abbreviations

ACU - Average Cattle Unit

CLM - Common Land Mapping

CVS - Charagah Vikas Samiti

GP - Gram Panchayat

GPS - Global Positioning System

MGNREGA - Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act

MGNREGS - Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme

MIS - Management Information System

MSL - Mean Sea Level

NDVI - Normalised Difference Vegetation Index

NGO - Non-Governmental Organisation

NRM - Natural Resource Management

PLPC - Public Land Protection Cell

PRA - Panchayati Raj Act

PRI - Panchayati Raj Institutions

RD&PR - Rural Development and Panchayati Raj

SHG - Self Help Group

ST - Scheduled Tribes

Rationale

This Atlas aims to stimulate imagination around Commons, provide pathways to access place-based information, and celebrate community stewardship practices. It foregrounds communities as full partners in this long-term journey of listening to one another, organising, gathering information, and communicating ideas.

This puts communities in a better position to represent themselves, create open information and knowledge assets, and engage in data-enabled deliberations with a broad range of actors across the ecosystem.

By doing this, we believe that communities can mobilise community-led action on multiple fronts and influence local decision-making processes over natural resources. This concerted approach will not only build the agency, autonomy, and capacities of local communities but also enable them to exercise greater power.

Introduction

India is a powerhouse of biodiversity, with a vast range of species that support various habitats and ecosystems. As the world grapples with the challenges of climate change, India can play a significant role in protecting, conserving, and restoring the environment. According to estimates, the country has the potential to restore nearly 140 million hectares of landscapes, which can sequester 3 to 4.3 billion tons of above-ground carbon by 2040 [1]. Such restoration efforts can provide various benefits, such as biodiversity conservation, increased water availability, better soil nutrient management, and improved pollination services [2]. It can also generate sustainable livelihood opportunities and ensure improved socio-economic outcomes [3].

Recognising this role, governmental policies, programs, and initiatives have set ambitious goals for improving green cover and protecting biodiversity. To achieve long-lasting impact and sustainability in natural resource management, it is crucial to involve local communities in the process by formalising community tenure over natural assets and co-creating sustainable conservation regimes [4].

Commons, Communities and Ecology

Commons, such as pastures, water bodies, and forests, are resources that the local communities collectively access, use and manage. Over 350 million rural people in India depend on Commons for their livelihoods [5], including those from the dryland and semi-arid areas who derive 84 to 100% of their life

essentials from these resources [6]. These benefits may take the form of direct goods and services, such as timber, fuelwood, fodder, medicines, and water for irrigation and domestic use; or as a broad range of ecosystem services critical for agricultural and livestock production systems, food security, and local biodiversity. The material and non-material benefits derived from Commons have been estimated to be worth USD 90.5 billion [7].

However, unsustainable land use practices have led to immense pressure on these ecosystems, resulting in the rapid decline of Commons. For instance, India's total grassland area alone lost 31% or 5.65 hectares during 2005 and 2015 [8]. This has led to fragmentation and often complete loss of biodiversity, eroding the ecosystem's capacity to sequester carbon, purify air or retain moisture.

The decline of Commons directly affects the lives of those who depend on them. In the era of the Anthropocene and the unfolding climate crisis, the poor, landless, and marginalised will be disproportionately affected by these negative consequences [9]. Their capacities to adapt to changing realities will also be tested. Therefore, it is critical to conserve, protect, and manage Commons through tenurial mechanisms that empower communities and make them the purveyor of both ecological and economic benefits. A healthy Commons can restore ecological health, provide opportunities for alternative livelihoods, and build community resilience.

Community Stewardship of Commons

Commons have been part of the traditional resource management systems for generations, with local communities managing these resources in a way that allows them to benefit from them over the long-term. In some cases, local communities hold legal rights to participate in resource governance through constitutional safeguards and national and sub-national legal instruments. However, they often face challenges in effectively exercising their rights and participating in decision-making processes. These challenges can stem from a variety of factors, including a lack of recognition of community rights, limited capacities and resources, and historical marginalisation.

Community stewardship of Commons is an approach that recognises the critical role of local communities in the sustainable use and management of natural resources. It is based on the principle that communities, being the direct users of natural resources, are best placed to manage and govern them. It requires active community participation in the planning, decision-making, and implementation of activities, acknowledging the close relationship between communities and their local environment and the need to balance environmental, social, and economic considerations.

There are multiple benefits of community stewardship of shared resources. They include:

- **Strengthening agency of local communities:** Community stewardship mechanisms empowers communities to take ownership of their natural resources and participate in their management actively. This sense of ownership creates a feeling of responsibility and accountability, which can lead to more sustainable resource management practices.

- **Prioritising sustainable resource use:** Involvement of communities in natural resource management ensures that those directly dependent on the resources are motivated to use them sustainably.
- **Increasing access to livelihoods:** Community stewardship creates new opportunities for communities to generate income from their natural resources. This can include sustainable harvesting and selling of forest products, increase in fodder for livestock rearing, and sustainable fishing practices.
- **Promoting transparency and accountability:** Community stewardship is based on the principles of good governance, including transparency, accountability, and participation. By involving communities in the decision-making and governance of natural resources, they ensure that these principles are upheld.

Community Mapping for Stewardship

Commons is a complex ecosystem where local communities, governments, and civil society interact, yet information on the Commons and the extent of community dependence is generally lacking. To bridge the gap between life at the community level and the policy sphere, we find that mapping practices can facilitate richer engagement amongst the communities, and enable information-led discussions with the state functionaries.

Although practices of community mapping stand outside the norm of dominant map-making exercises that declare administrative limits or communicate political boundaries, these maps help communities speak to power and map their own geographies and realities in a definite space and time. The community mapping process offers many specific advantages, including building existing solidarities, deepening democratic practices, enabling the horizontal distribution of knowledge, strengthening local values, capturing community needs, and dispelling myths around communities' abilities to navigate and solve complex problems.

Therefore, we see community maps as stories from the ground, stories of a special genre. They are not lists, codes, categories or databases; they are not made out of context. Rather, they take on a life of their own as they weave multiple threads, however partially or episodically that may be. They signify the practical details and realities of everyday life, with their loose and informal ways of speaking. While incongruent with standard mapping practices, community maps shed light on various human-space interactions and alternate worldviews that do not find space in mainstream maps.

Commons contribute to the following Sustainable Development Goals:

Legal Architecture in Rajasthan

The Rajasthan Panchayati Raj Act 1994 (PRA 1994) defines common lands as lands that are not in exclusive possession and use of any individual but are commonly used by the inhabitants of local areas. Gram Panchayats are the custodians of common lands at the village level [10]. They ensure that these lands are sustainably and equitably managed for the benefit of all community members. To this end, the PRA 1994 and the rules framed thereunder empower the Panchayats to regulate, manage and develop pasture lands, water bodies, and other community assets within their jurisdiction. Panchayats are further required to maintain an asset register of all the immovable properties vested in or placed at their disposal [11]. The PRA 1994 also mandates the constitution of a standing committee for development and production programmes, including those related to agriculture, animal husbandry, minor irrigation, cooperation, cottage industries, and other allied subjects [12].

At the state level, the control and management of these resources fall under the purview of the state Revenue Department and the Department of Rural Development and Panchayati Raj (RD&PR). A myriad of state legislations provides for the protection and conservation of Commons. For instance, the Rajasthan Tenancy Act 1955 prohibits the acquisition of *khatadari* or tenancy from on pasture lands [14]. Rules framed under the Rajasthan Land Revenue Act 1956 also safeguard pasture lands from diversion or allotment for alternate uses such as agriculture [15], the development of private forests [16], or the establishment of lime kilns [17]. If pasture lands have to be set apart for other purposes, the Rajasthan Tenancy (Government)

Key Functions of Panchayats related to Commons [13]

- Removal of encroachments on public properties;
- Making surveys;
- Control of cattle stands, threshing floors, grazing grounds and community lands;
- Preparation, maintenance and upkeep of Panchayat records;
- Development of wastelands;
- Development and maintenance of grazing lands and preventing their unauthorised alienation and use;
- Grassland development;
- Development of fisheries in the villages;
- Planting and preservation of trees on public lands under their control;
- Fuel plantations and fodder development;
- Control and maintenance of tanks irrigating up to 50 acres;
- Promotion of rural and cottage industries;
- Constructions, repairs and maintenance of drinking water wells, tanks and ponds;
- Maintenance and regulation of burning and burial grounds;
- Maintenance of community assets;
- Construction and maintenance of cattle sheds, ponds, and cart stands;
- Maintenance of public parks and playgrounds.

Rules 1955 make it mandatory for the district collector to consult the Panchayats [18]. The collector also has the power to set apart an equal area of unoccupied government land, if available, as pasture lands in the same village. However, in 2017, the Hon'ble High Court of Rajasthan ruled that the collector's power to change the classification of the pasture lands should be exercised sparingly. Preservation and development of pastures were deemed to be the rule, and diversion thereof only an exception [19].

In case of encroachments on common lands, the Rajasthan Land Revenue Act 1956 empowers the *tehsildar* to summarily evict the trespassers, impose fines, and order the removal of crops, buildings or other constructions on such lands. Following the landmark ruling of the Hon'ble Supreme Court of India in the case of *Jagpal Singh vs. State of Punjab* in 2011 [20], the RD&PR department of Rajasthan issued a circular to demarcate all common lands recorded in the revenue records, update the asset registers, and issue orders for the removal of encroachments [21].

An Impetus Towards Decentralised Governance

In 2009, Rajasthan became the first state to establish the Rajasthan Wasteland Development Board to formulate policies and devise strategies for the development of 'wastelands' in the state. In 2016, the Board was renamed the "Wasteland and Pastureland Development Board", emphasising the protection and conservation of the state's pasture lands. This move aimed to address the livelihoods of the majority of the rural communities that rely on livestock rearing. The Board is empowered to play a crucial role in promoting sustainable land use practices, generating livelihoods, building capacities of stakeholders, and addressing the challenges of land degradation and desertification in Rajasthan.

In 2017, the architecture under the Rajasthan Wasteland Development Board was further strengthened by establishing the Banjar Bhoomi Evam Charagah Vikas Samitis at the district, block and village level. These committees are headed by the *pramukh* of Zilla Parishad, the Block *pradhan* of Panchayat Samiti, and the *sarpanch* of Panchayat, respectively. The constitution of these committees reflects the commitment to enhance the convergence between the RD&PR, Revenue and Agriculture departments. This architecture was designed to improve the management and governance of common lands by demarcating them, removing encroachments, and developing restoration plans through MGNREGS.

The most recent development occurred in 2019 when the Rajasthan government directed each district to establish a Public Land Protection Cell (PLPC) under the leadership of the district collector. [22] The PLPC is responsible for ensuring prompt and effective resolution of cases related to encroachments on common lands. Previously, the state judiciary was overwhelmed with public interest litigations regarding such encroachments and the resulting loss of traditional livelihoods and depleting natural resources. With this initiative, Rajasthan became the first state to establish a decentralised mechanism for protecting common lands and enabling access to justice at the district level, inspiring other states like Madhya Pradesh and Assam to establish PLPCs in their states.

Chittorgarh at a Glance

Chittorgarh district, located in the southeastern part of Rajasthan, is a historically and culturally significant region. It spans a total area of 7,822 square kilometres, accounting for 3.17% of the state's total area. The district is known for its majestic forts, ancient temples, and rich heritage, attracting visitors from far and wide.

Geographically, Chittorgarh district shares its borders with Bhilwara and Bundi districts to the north, Kota district to the east, Udaipur and Rajsamand districts to the west, and Pratapgarh district along with the state of Madhya Pradesh to the south. The topography of the district is characterised by undulating terrain, with a gradual slope from south to north. While the western, southern and northern parts of the district are relatively flat, the overall landscape of Chittorgarh is diverse and captivating. This is enhanced by the presence of the Banas and Gambhiri rivers which flow gracefully through its surroundings. The Banas River Basin covers a significant portion of the district, while the eastern region falls within the Chambal River Basin, and the southern part is in the Mahi River Basin. [23]

Chittorgarh and its surrounding areas are home to a variety of wildlife and avian species. The region also has a unique and specialised flora that has adapted to survive in arid conditions, such as *Prosopis cineraria* (Khejri), *Anogeissus pendula* (Dhok), and *Acacia leucophloea* (Phulai). Chittorgarh is also graced with a few wetland ecosystems, including the Bassi Wildlife Sanctuary, that attract migratory birds and support aquatic plants and animals.

S. No.	Block	No. of Gram Panchayats	No. of Villages
1	Badi Sadri	26	162
2	Begun	31	264
3	Bhadesar	25	170
4	Bhainsrorgarh	27	213
5	Bhopalsagar	19	90
6	Chittorgarh	40	233
7	Dungla	26	117
8	Gangrar	22	133
9	Kapasan	23	117
10	Nimbahera	37	179
11	Rashmi	23	94
Total		299	1772

Table 1: Administrative division of Chittorgarh district [24]

The soil composition in the district exhibits considerable diversity. The region is characterised by red loamy soil, black soil, brown soil, yellowish brown soil, and alluvial soils. The presence of black soils in areas like Dungla, Kapasan, Begun, and parts of Rashmi tehsils contributes to the district's agricultural potential. Yellowish brown soils are predominant in Chittorgarh, Nimbahera, Bhopalsagar, Bhainsrorgarh, and Bhadesar. Hilly soils occur in Bhainsrorgarh, Begun, Chittorgarh, Dungla, and Nimbahera.

Additionally, the banks of the Banas river are marked by stretches of light sandy loam soils.

Chittorgarh is renowned as the “limestone district” of Rajasthan, due to its abundant deposits of cement-grade limestone. The region also has significant reserves of sandstone, which is widely used for house flooring. Additionally, smaller deposits of china clay, red ochre, silica sand, quartz, feldspar, granite, and copper ore also contribute to the district's mineral wealth.

According to the Census 2011, Chittorgarh had a population of 1.54 million, accounting for approximately 2.25% of Rajasthan's total population. The district's population is predominantly concentrated in rural areas, with 81.53% residing in rural regions. Its economy is primarily agrarian, with agriculture being the mainstay of the rural population. The district is known for its production of crops such as wheat, maize, soybean, millets, and pulses.

Map of Chittorgarh

Chittorgarh district, situated in the southern part of Rajasthan, is bordered by Bhilwara and Bundi districts to the north, Kota district to the east, Udaipur and Rajsamand districts to the west, and Pratapgarh district to the south, along with the state of Madhya Pradesh. The district is administratively divided into 11 blocks, and has a total of 1,772 towns and villages.

Common Lands of Chittorgarh

Common lands play a crucial role in rural ecosystems, serving as vital spaces for grazing animals, and as a source of food and fuel for local communities. Here, common lands constitute pasturelands, forests and wastelands.

Pasturelands of Chittorgarh

Pasturelands, despite their critical importance, are frequently undervalued. Not only do they serve as a valuable food source for livestock, but they also contribute to erosion control and soil quality improvement. Within Chittorgarh, approximately 64% of the villages (1,119) possess pasturelands, constituting up to 20% of their total geographical area. About 420 villages do not have any pasturelands at all.

Wastelands of Chittorgarh

The term 'wasteland' originated during colonial times as a social construct, based on the perception that such areas do not directly contribute to the exchequer. However, according to the NSSO (1998), wastelands serve as de facto Commons. The legal framework in Rajasthan also allows for the conversion of wastelands to pasturelands.

Mapping the Commons

Establishing clear boundaries is essential for identifying community resources, facilitating resource planning, and ensuring transparency in action. To map their common lands, the communities of Chittorgarh used a digital application called the Common Land Mapping (CLM) tool, developed by the India Observatory <<https://www.indiaobservatory.org.in/>>. This tool utilises geo-referencing to identify and demarcate land resources. Once users achieve accurate GPS readings, they can record the location points along the land boundaries on the device and upload them to the cloud.

In Chittorgarh, the active involvement of community members played a crucial role in the data collection process. Through their participation in collectives, they actively tracked and identified boundaries using existing maps. This process quickly highlighted

the significance of mapping, empowering the communities to assert their knowledge and reclaim agency while distributing leadership across the collective. The adoption of community mapping practices across the district demonstrated that it not only strengthened place-based knowledge systems but also empowered the communities. By collecting spatial data and working with maps, community members gained leverage in their deliberations with civil society members and government officials.

The maps presented in this Atlas were produced through a two-pronged approach: (1) Using primary data from the community mapping exercise across the district, and (2) Overlaying existing open access datasets/ layers onto administrative boundaries. These two approaches are further explained in the flowchart below.

Villages with Community Institutions

Community institutions serve as the cornerstone of rural societies, providing the foundation for local economies, cultures, and social structures. In the last four years, dedicated efforts by local communities have led to the establishment of Charagah Vikas Samitis (CVS) in 61% (922) of the total villages. These institutions are formed to effectively manage, protect, and conserve pasturelands at the village level.

Local communities often have a deep connection to their immediate environment, possessing a wealth of knowledge around traditional ecological practices. Rooted in a rich history and heritage, these communities have assumed the mantle of conservation across generations. Driven by a collective spirit, they embrace the power of unity and collaboration. They come together to establish rules and regulations that ensure fair access and utilisation of resources. This communal fabric fosters an ongoing dialogue, providing a sacred space for regular community-level consultations. Within this exchange, knowledge is shared, wisdom is passed down, and diverse perspectives converge, creating a holistic framework that nurtures both communities and the environment. With a profound sensitivity to local needs and priorities, and an unwavering commitment to honouring and preserving nature, the efforts of these communities stand testament to the profound truth: that life flourishes when nurtured by those who deeply cherish its magnificence.

Villages where Pasturelands were Mapped

Community mapping activities were carried out in approximately 950 villages, covering a total land area of around 46,000 hectares. The majority of the mapping efforts were undertaken in the blocks of Kapasan (302 villages), Chittorgarh (295), Begun (196), and Bari Sadri (186).

Pasturelands Mapped in Chittorgarh

46,000 hectares of common lands are spread across the district into approximately 1,790 patches of land. A significant portion of the mapped area, close to 98%, consist of village pasturelands. The remaining portion are classified as revenue wastelands, which the communities de facto utilise for livestock grazing purposes.

Improving Pasturelands for Resilient Ecosystems

Livestock grazing is a centuries-old practice where animals like cattle, goats, sheep, and camels feed on natural vegetation in diverse landscapes. In India, different communities collectively rear livestock, regardless of their landholding status. They manage common pastures using time-honoured techniques and practices, which etch a profound impact on their social and cultural heritage.

Livestock keeping contributes significantly to food security and poverty reduction, particularly in regions facing climatic uncertainty and resource scarcity. Its role in sustaining livelihoods and building social-ecological resilience is increasingly recognised in the ongoing climate crisis [25] [26]. Sustainable grazing practices are also crucial for biodiversity preservation as they maintain the growth of diverse vegetation, enhance soil quality, and connect different ecosystems through livestock mobility [27]. Grasslands, which account for a third of global terrestrial carbon stocks, further serve as vital carbon sinks. [28] However, despite numerous benefits, pastures and pastoralism often face neglect and a lack of appreciation. Land-use changes driven by increasing consumption patterns have led to a decline in the availability and quality of pastures, creating pressure on pastoral communities and the overall ecosystem.

Significance of Pastures in Rajasthan

In Rajasthan, where rainfall is erratic and droughts are common, grazing-based animal husbandry is integral to the rural economy.

Over 80% of rural households engage in livestock keeping, resulting in a staggering total of 56.8 million livestock across the state [29]. During 2022-23, the gross value addition from the livestock sector was worth USD 22 billion, accounting for 46% of the value added by the entire agriculture and allied sectors [30]. In economic terms, the ecosystem services provided by Rajasthan's pastures are worth USD 1.6 million annually [7].

Rajasthan is also home to pastoral communities including the Raika, Gujjar, Jat, Sindhi Muslims, Rath Muslims, and Gairi, whose livelihoods have long depended on livestock rearing. To them, pastoralism is both a source of income and a way of life that is deeply rooted in their cultural heritage. With an intimate understanding of their local environment, some communities have developed transhumant practices, where they move their herds to different grazing grounds within Rajasthan and neighbouring states based on the seasons.

Conserving and protecting pastures are essential for the sustainable development of rural communities in Rajasthan. With 4.07 million acres of permanent pastures and 13.4 million acres of wastelands [31], Rajasthan can also significantly contribute to the country's restoration targets. It is thus important to prioritise efforts towards promoting sustainable land-use practices, strengthening communal tenure systems, and conserving pastures in the state.

Livestock and Pastures

We used data from the Livestock Census (2019) to calculate the average cattle unit (ACU) per village. We then compared it against the available pastureland data obtained from the open-access portal, Dhara. Through this exercise, 89% of the villages (904) were found to have insufficient pasturelands to meet the requirements of their existing livestock count.

Community Efforts for Sustainable Pasture Development:

The Case of Kharkhanda

Overexploitation of groundwater and frequent droughts have left the Gangrar block of Chittorgarh with limited water for irrigation. [32] The rural communities in the region thus greatly depend on rearing livestock for their income. In Kharkhanda village, the communities rely on 213.3 hectares of *charagah* (pasture lands) for fodder for livestock. However, issues such as overgrazing, declining ecological health and reduced carrying capacity of the pastures were making it difficult to maintain a sustainable herd.

In 2020, the community of Kharkhanda came together to address these issues by forming the *Charagah Vikas Samiti* (Pasture Land Development Committee) at the village level. The *Samiti* first mapped the pasture lands to establish boundaries and to aid the decision-making processes. They held several rounds of meetings with the community members to discuss the importance of Commons for their livelihoods and for maintaining the ecological balance. With training and technical support from a local NGO, resolutions were passed to remove encroachments from the pasture lands and to implement restoration works.

The 27-year-old *sarpanch* of the Panchayat played a key role in inspiring collective action, thereby demonstrating the power of the youth to catalyse change for ecological conservation. Working

with the chairman of the *Samiti*, he mobilised support from the village community to remove invasive species like *jarmeri* (*Lantana camara*) and *vilayati babool* (*Prosopis juliflora*) from the pasture lands. The *Samiti* then facilitated restoration projects like digging trenches, bunds, and traditional rainwater harvesting structures called *naadis*. To support this, resources were mobilised from programmes such as the Rajiv Gandhi Jal Sanchay Yojana and MGNREGS.

The results of the community's efforts have been remarkable. The restoration works improved the moisture retention in the pasture lands, thereby increasing the availability of grass and vegetation as fodder. This led more families to keep livestock as a source of income, further resulting in a significant increase in dairy production in the village. Through their efforts, the community of Kharkhanda has demonstrated that livelihoods can be improved, even in challenging conditions, by working together. “*Moving forward, works related to natural resource management will be given priority to protect our Commons*”, stated the *sarpanch* of Kharkhanda.

MGNREGS Assets Created in Chittorgarh

Under the MGNREGS, communities have the opportunity to engage in various activities such as water conservation and harvesting structures, renovation of traditional water bodies, and land development. This map highlights the villages (205) where community-led initiatives have resulted in the creation of public assets aimed at restoring and preserving natural resources.

The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS) was introduced in 2005 as a social protection program. It provides 100 days of wage employment in a financial year to every rural household whose adult members volunteer for unskilled manual work. This scheme offers employment opportunities and promotes sustainable livelihoods in rural areas, particularly during the lean agricultural season. Its impact has been significant, as it has played a vital role in reducing rural poverty, curbing migration to urban areas, strengthening community-based institutions, and empowering women and other marginalised communities with equal opportunities.

A substantial proportion of community assets created under the MGNREGS are related to Natural Resource Management (NRM) infrastructure, including check dams, farm ponds and other water harvesting structures. These initiatives have had positive effects by enhancing water availability, improving soil health, and increasing green cover in rural areas. A collaborative study conducted in 2022 by FES in partnership with the Government of Rajasthan found that NRM works carried out under the MGNREGS led to increased groundwater levels, resulting in expanded irrigated areas and total land under cultivation, which in turn resulted in higher crop yields and incomes. These efforts also improve fodder and water availability for livestock, benefiting poorer households the most. [33] This underscores the potential of the MGNREGS in reducing the vulnerability of rural and marginalised communities to the impacts of climate change. By investing in NRM infrastructure, the scheme not only provides employment but also contributes to long-term environmental sustainability and resilience.

Reviving MGNREGS in Arthala to Enhance Local Livelihoods

The role played by the MGNREGS in improving socio-economic conditions and promoting inclusive development is widely known. However, in the small village of Arthala situated in the Dunga block of Chittorgarh, the village community had low awareness regarding their rights under the MGNREGA. They were uninformed of its potential to enhance their livelihood opportunities while addressing land degradation. Due to this, the village community was not proactive in planning and submitting action plans under the MGNREGS.

Despite the difficulties faced due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the year 2020 initiated a process of change within Arthala. Recognising the degradation of their village pastures (of a size of 62 hectares) and its impact on their livelihoods, the village community came together to form a *Charagah Vikas Samiti*. The main objective of this *Samiti* was to develop pasture lands by adopting sustainable soil and water conservation measures. Key to this agenda was formally including the activities in the village development plans and actively leveraging MGNREGS to drive change.

Since 2021, MGNREGS witnessed a renaissance in Arthala. Through the *Samiti*, the community identified several

opportunities to increase water availability, improve soil health and enhance moisture retention of the pasture lands. Detailed plans were prepared to undertake restoration works like digging cattle-proof trenches, planting local tree and shrub species, and deepening the existing traditional water harvesting structures called *naadis*. A total budget of Rs. 36.51 lakhs was estimated for the endeavour, and plans were submitted to authorities for approval under the MGNREGS. Once the activities were sanctioned, the restoration works began within the village.

These efforts are already showing positive results. Since 2021, a total of 110 families from the village have worked on restoration projects estimated at Rs. 14.39 lakhs. Wage employment under the MGNREGS has enabled each of these families to earn an annual income between Rs. 15 to 19 thousand, thereby helping to stabilise and secure their livelihoods. *"I had been thinking of repairing my house for a few years and was saving money for it. Extra income from MGNREGS increased my savings so I could get the repairs done."*, said Kisan Rawat.

With time, as the local ecology improves, the community will reap higher benefits from their collective efforts.

Tracking Changes in Natural Resources

NDVI maps are effective tools for comparing the previous and current states of vegetation and water bodies across different years. The provided map illustrates the notable improvements in vegetation cover and water bodies.

October - 2018

Tracking Changes in Natural Resources

Such maps facilitate data-enabled discussions among communities, empowering them to make informed decisions regarding the management of natural resources. By presenting data in accessible and visually comprehensible formats, these maps democratise information, enabling community members to actively participate in decision-making processes and establish long-term goals for sustainable management and restoration of their natural ecosystems.

October - 2022

Changes in Vegetation of Chittorgarh

Land use changes over large areas of land have the potential to significantly alter long-term ecosystem dynamics. To capture and understand these transformations, the NDVI (Normalised Difference Vegetation Index) can be a valuable method. NDVI enables us to monitor and evaluate long-term changes in surface resources using remote sensing and satellite data.

Way Forward

Local communities have long been the stewards of land and other natural resources. Their deep understanding of their local environment has enabled them to maintain a sustainable way of life for generations. Unfortunately, their efforts to protect and conserve the environment have often been overlooked or even actively undermined. However, there is now a growing recognition of the vital role that local communities play in environmental conservation. There is a wider acceptance of the knowledge and expertise these communities possess. Therefore, it is imperative to build stronger relationships and solidarities within these communities – listen and learn from their collective knowledge and experiences.

Ecological restoration, particularly of the pasturelands, is crucial for the sustainable development and equitable distribution of resources among local communities in Chittorgarh. Nevertheless, the existing measures have yet to achieve their full potential, and there is a long way to go. In this context, we explore the way forward for restoration under social schemes such as MGNREGS, and increased governance through institutional building.

A. Identify and Demarcate Common Resources

Clear resource boundaries are the essential first step towards effective governance of Commons. They provide a basis for determining the rights and responsibilities associated with natural resources, enabling institutions to establish rules for sustainable management and preventing conflicts, land grabbing, and encroachments.

However, identifying the extent and distribution of Commons is also important. This requires assessing the availability and accessibility of common resources, as well as their relationship with the livelihood dependence and socio-cultural context of the community. Such assessment can help identify the specific needs of the community and design interventions for sustainable land management that are tailored to the local context.

B. Strengthen Community Tenure over Natural Resources

The extent to which formal systems recognise and protect customary rights held by the local communities is a critical factor in ensuring effective local governance. Such efforts ensure that the village communities can make secure investments to restore, manage, and protect the natural resources [34], and improve their ability to adapt to climate change [35]. It further fosters community participation and empowerment, leading to the development of stronger and more resilient communities.

To achieve this, appropriate tenorial arrangements should be evolved that recognise the rights to own, access, use, or manage the resources, so as to strengthen the rights of the communities over their Commons. Institutions such as the Banjar Bhoomi Evam Charagah Vikas Samitis and PLPCs at the district-level support this endeavour. Further steps can be taken to ensure the inclusion of these resources into community records such as the panchayat asset registers, allowing communities to exercise greater control over resources by tracking and monitoring their

status. By doing so, communities can make informed decisions about the use and management of their natural resources and safeguard them for future generations.

C. Enable Collective Governance through Community Institutions

The success of restoration initiatives is closely tied to how effectively and inclusively they are governed. It depends on how authority is devolved to the lowest levels to encourage participatory modes of decision-making. Such efforts can be successfully replicated through institutional building, which involves building the capacity of local institutions to manage natural resources effectively. This can be achieved through contextual training, refresher sessions and the use of asynchronous communication tools to provide assistance to local institutions. By doing so, stakeholders can be made aware of the importance of restoration activities, and critical partnerships can be forged and strengthened between government agencies, NGOs, and other stakeholders.

Institutional building can be implemented at various levels, such as at the village, block, district, and state levels. Further, committees such as Charagah Vikas Samitis or panchayat-recognised NRM sub-committee at the village level can provide necessary training and support for sustainable management of Commons.

D. Increase the Scope of Commons Restoration under MGNREGS

Over the years, restoration of Commons has been a significant focus of the MGNREGS program to enhance rural livelihoods.

The scheme provides wage employment to rural households for up to 100 days per year, which can be utilised for various activities. While MGNREGS can be used to create public assets such as shared rural infrastructure, there is still potential to increase the allocation of funds for NRM-related works to support Commons restoration.

To achieve this, local communities, government functionaries, and NGOs can collaborate to identify opportunities and establish linkages with initiatives like the Jal Shakti Abhiyan. Generating awareness among stakeholders about the importance of Commons and its role in improving rural livelihoods is essential. This approach could create direct employment opportunities under restoration projects and indirect ones in areas such as livestock rearing, fodder production, and other related activities.

Facilitators

A cadre of 22 field trainers led the community mapping efforts across Chittorgarh. They walked alongside their communities, leaving imprints of progress with each step as they traced the boundaries of the Commons that sustained the community. Tirelessly, they organised training workshops to empower their communities to take charge of their resources. Later, they shared their experiences and insights with the editorial team of this Atlas, and we will be forever grateful for their invaluable contributions and for bringing this knowledge to the fore. We also thank Sanwar Lal Jat for coordinating the community mapping initiatives and facilitating the development of this Atlas.

Asha Khajwaniya
Bhainsroadgarh

Devendra Tripathi
Kapasan

Devishanker Sukhwil
Rashmi

Dinesh Pareek
Rashmi

Goverdhan Jat
Chittorgarh

Hitesh Tank
Bhadesar

Kaiash Pareek
Rashmi

Laxmi Lal Parjapat
Badisadri

Manjeet Sharma,
Nimbaheda

Manju Sharma
Kapasan

Omparkash Meghwal
Chittorgarh

Rahul Sharma
Dungla

Rajendara Singh Chundawat
Bhupalsagar

Raju Gurjar
Gangrar

Rameshwar Meena
Badisadri

Rampal Sharma
Gangrar

Ratan Lal Mali
Bhupalsagar

Sanjiv Jat
Chittorgarh

Sanwar Lal Jat
Chittorgarh

Sunil Tank
Chittorgarh

Sunita Bunker
Gangrar

Sunita Rajpur
Gangrar

Vijay Vergiye
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- Provided that in case where the area of the land sought to be so allotted or seipare exceeds 4 hectares, the Collector shall obtain prior permission of the State Government:
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Notes

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